

On simple Physics model behind allometric egg size empirical equation of Calder, 1984

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Abstract: Calder has given an empirical formula relating egg length to it's mass $l = 1.51 m^{0.34}$, where output is egg size in cm and egg mass is inputed in grams. However, this relationship is strictly empirical. I show here that this allometric relationship is merely the outcome of egg geometry and it's basic physical properties.

Determining egg size from it's physical properties

Egg geometry can be approximated as sphere of volume $V = 4/3\pi R^3$, which has mean density $\rho = \frac{m}{V}$. Given that egg size is just $l = 2R$, one can derive mathematical relationship of egg size from these facts :

$$l = \left(\frac{6m}{\pi\rho} \right)^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

where m is egg mass in kg and ρ is egg density. So for egg size we have arrived at analytical equation in the form

$$l = \alpha m^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

We need to express α as:

$$\alpha = 100 \times \left(\frac{6 \times 1000^{-1}}{\pi\rho} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

1000^{-1} factor is because Calder empirical formula takes mass in grams and $100 \times$ factor is due to the need to get egg size output in cm as helping us for arriving to the same Calder allometric expression. Substituting egg mean density $1031 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ (which is by the way close to room's temperature water density) into (3) equation, we get $\alpha \approx 1.23$. Which transforms eq (2) into

$$l = 1.23m^{0.33}$$

This is very close to a Calder's empirical egg size expression.

Comparison of Calder allometric expression with the one derived here analytically

Below is a plot composed of Calder egg size function and same size function derived analytically :

Calculated correlation coefficient between analytical and empirical forms is 0.99, which is quite good. Mismatch of functions or analytical solution errors could be explained that eggs may have variability in density; bad average egg density used; egg geometry assumption error - eggs are not an ideal sphere, but rather an ellipsoid like structure. These error explaining hypotheses must be tested further.

Conclusions

Using egg physical and geometrical properties, namely sphere geometry and egg density, analytical expression (1) defining relation between egg size and its mass was derived.

I have found 0.99 correlation coefficient between derived analytical expression (1) and Calder given allometric formula $l = 1.51 m^{0.34}$, this proves the point that analytical formula may be used as well predicting egg sizes. There are model fitting errors, which must be researched further. It's interesting to note that Calder in one of his works gives thickness of mammalian skin based on body mass $h(mm) = 0.87 \times \text{mass}^{0.29}$. Another idea for a research is that it may be not a simple coincidence that exponent is also close to 1/3,- mammalian skin thickness *may* be also derived from a volumetric model of an animal body, given that cell division processes and body scaling of animals should comply to the same biological rules.

References

1. "Variations in the Thickness and Composition of the Skin of the Giraffe", Farzana Sathar, N. Ludo Badlangana, Paul R. Manger, 20 August 2010.
2. "Size, function, and life history", WA Calder, 1996.